

Synthesis of 1-Substituted Phenyl-2-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-(*p*-NN-*bis*-2'-Cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-Pyrrolidones

V. S. JOLLY*, S. P. SINGH** and A. K. SHRIVASTAVA

Dept. of Chemistry, Maharaja College, Chhatarpur-471 001

Manuscript received 12 November 1981, revised 28 July 1982, accepted 20 May 1983

with β -aroyl propionic acid in presence of fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride and formation of α - (*p* - NN-*bis*-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)- γ -phenyl- $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -butenolides (I).

(I)

The butenolides (I) on heating with aromatic amines gave 1-substituted phenyl-2-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-(*p*-NN-*bis*-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-pyrrolidones (II) in good yields.

(II)

SUBSTITUTED nitrogen and oxygen heterocyclics and their derivatives have been reported as antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴⁻⁵ and insecticidal⁶ agents and as therapeutics⁷⁻¹³. Effectiveness of the drugs is enhanced by cyanoethylation¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

The use of cyanoethylated aldehydes for the synthesis of lactones and their derivatives has not been reported so far. In view of the interesting properties of the cyanoethylated compounds, nitrogen mustard type compounds and pyrrolidones, it seemed worthwhile to combine these structural features in lactones and pyrrolidones.

The present investigation records the condensation of 4-NN-*bis*-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF α - (*p*-NN-*bis*-2'-CYANOETHYLAMINO BENZYLIDENE)- γ -SUBSTITUTED PHENYL- $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -BUTENOLIDES (I)

No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Colour	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
1	H	H	H	H	Orange-yellow	173	76.8	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂	11.89 (11.38)
2	H	H	Me	H	Deep-yellow	182	58.5	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂	10.39 (10.96)
3	H	Me	Me	H	Red	163	69.3	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂	10.23 (10.58)
4	Me	H	Me	H	Brown-red	157	60.0	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂	10.12 (10.58)
5	Me	H	Me	Me	Brown-red	165	63.3	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₂	10.92 (10.58)
6	H	H	OMe	H	Dark-brown	178	59.2	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂	10.11 (10.55)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-2-HYDROXY-2-PHENYL-4-(*p*-NN-*bis*-2'-CYANOETHYLAMINO BENZYLIDENE)-5-PYRROLIDONES (II)

No.	R	Colour	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
7	H	Light-yellow	215	63.4	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄	12.56 (12.12)
8	Me(<i>o</i> -)	Yellow	211	57.4	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄	11.17 (11.76)
9	Me(<i>m</i> -)	Yellow	213	51.6	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄	12.09 (11.76)
10	Me(<i>p</i> -)	Light-yellow	217	59.5	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄	11.37 (11.76)
11	Cl(<i>o</i> -)	Yellow	223	48.3	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	11.97 (11.28)
12	Cl(<i>m</i> -)	Yellow	229	46.3	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	10.98 (11.28)
13	Cl(<i>p</i> -)	Brown-yellow	228	50.4	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	11.73 (11.28)
14	OMe(<i>o</i> -)	Yellow	213	50.8	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	11.87 (11.38)
15	OMe(<i>m</i> -)	Orange-yellow	197	54.8	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	10.95 (10.38)
16	OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Deep-yellow	219	58.9	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	10.98 (11.38)
17	CO ₂ H(<i>o</i> -)	Yellow	207	43.5	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	10.89 (11.06)
18	SO ₃ H(<i>p</i> -)	Yellow	329	39.4	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	10.46 (10.33)

*Author for correspondence.

**Present address ; Research & Quality Control Division, Bansagar Project, Deolond, Rewa.

Potentiality of the new products as carcinostats is under investigation and shall be reported elsewhere.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected.

α -(*p*-NN-bis-2'-Cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)- γ -phenyl)- $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -butenolide (I, R=R₁=R₂=R₃=H). *General method*: An intimate mixture of β -benzoylpropionic acid¹⁸ (0.35 g), 4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde¹⁹ (0.25 g), fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride (1 ml) was placed in a round bottomed flask with an air condenser. The contents were heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. The orange-yellow crystals were washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 76.8%, m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 11.89. C₂₈H₁₉O₂N₄ requires N, 11.38%). IR absorption spectrum (KBr) shows characteristic band of $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -butenolide ring at 1770 cm⁻¹ and tertiary-N at 1320 cm⁻¹.

2-Hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl-4-(*p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-pyrrolidone (II, R = H): The butenolide (I, 1; 0.37 g) and redistilled aniline (0.1 g) were taken in a 50 ml round bottomed flask fitted with an air condenser and heated for 3 hr on a steam bath. The contents were cooled and acidified with aqueous hydrochloric acid when 2-hydroxy-1,2-diphenyl-4-(*p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-pyrrolidone separated as solid. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave light yellow needles of the product, yield 63.4%, m.p. 215°. (Found; N, 12.56. C₂₉H₂₀O₂N₄ requires N, 12.12%).

Other pyrrolidones (8 to 18) were prepared in a similar way.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for ir spectra and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Research Fellowships (S.P.S. and A.K.S.).

References

1. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 985; 1976, 53, 163, 371, 827; 1977, 54, 634.
2. A. KABRA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 989; 1977, 54, 508.
3. N. N. JOSHI and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 1081.
4. F. S. G. SOLIMAN and R. M. SHARIK, *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, 83, 193164b.
5. B. NANDA, S. PADMANAVAN, B. TRIPATHY and A. S. MITTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 533.
6. S. A. AGRIPAT, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 29699z.
7. J. B. WRIGHT, W. E. DULIN and J. H. MARKILLIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 102.
8. R. H. IRSCHMANN, N. G. STFINBERG, E. F. SCHOENEWALDT, W. J. PALWEDA and MAX. TISCHLER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 352.
9. E. L. ANDERSON, J. E. CASEY, L. C. GREENE, J. J. JAFFERY, and H. E. REIFF, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 259.
10. V. S. JOLLY and C. M. AGRAWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 7, 743.
11. V. S. JOLLY, A. K. HALVE and A. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 12, 1117.

12. V. S. JOLLY, A. K. SHRIVASTAVA, S. P. SINGH and K. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 539.
13. V. S. JOLLY and A. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 949.
14. J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, 5, 38.
15. F. REVERDIN, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1523.
16. W. MARCKWALD and V. DROSTE, *Hullshoff Chem. Ber.*, 1899, 32, 560.
17. L. DEMENY, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas.*, 1931, 50, 51.
18. I. G. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd Edn., 1957, p. 737.
19. V. S. JOLLY and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 997.

Sorption Behaviour of Th⁴⁺, ZrO²⁺, UO₂²⁺ and Some Rare Earths on Collidinium Molybdoarsenate—Separation of Th⁴⁺

AJAY K. JAIN*, CHAND BALA,
SUSHMA AGRAWAL and RAJ P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee-247 667

Manuscript received 28 January 1982,
revised 18 December 1982, accepted 10 March 1983

THE insoluble salts of heteropolyacids are preferred to other inorganic ion exchangers as they usually exhibit selective ion exchange behaviour¹⁻³. However, the most widely used heteropolyacid salts, ammonium molybdo- and tungsto-phosphates, show dispersion tendency and need foreign support material for column operation^{4,5}. The present communication reports the sorption behaviour of UO₂²⁺, ZrO²⁺, Th⁴⁺ and some rare earths on a highly insoluble exchanger, collidinium molybdoarsenate (CMA)⁶, whose column has been successfully used for the separation of Th⁴⁺.

Experimental

Reagents and materials :

Collidinium molybdoarsenate, (C₈H₁₁NH)₈-Mo₁₂AsO₄₀ (CMA), was prepared as described earlier⁶. All metal salts used were of AR grade. The radiotracers ¹³⁴Cs, ⁸⁶Rb, ⁸⁸⁺⁸⁹Sr, ^{114m}+¹¹⁴In, ¹⁴¹Ce, ¹⁶⁰Tb and ⁹¹Y were obtained from B.A.R.C., Bombay.

Apparatus and procedure :

A well type scintillation counter was used for activity measurements of tracers except ⁹¹Y whose activity was determined on a G.M. counter⁷. UO₂²⁺ and ZrO²⁺ were determined spectrophotometrically⁸, whereas La³⁺ and Th⁴⁺ by EDTA titrations⁹. The distribution coefficient values (K_d) for various metals were determined and separation of Th⁴⁺ was carried on the column of the exchanger in the manner already described⁶.

Results and Discussion

It is seen from Table 1 that CMA shows affinity for ZrO²⁺, Th⁴⁺ and UO₂²⁺ in the order Th⁴⁺>